

Wind turbine aerodynamics scale-modeling for floating offshore wind platform testing

Albert M. Urbán¹, Raúl Guanche¹

¹ Environmental Hydraulics Institute, Universidad de Cantabria - Avda. Isabel Torres, 15, Parque Científico y Tecnológico de Cantabria, 39011, Santander, Spain

Abstract. Wave tank testing is a crucial step during the development of floating offshore wind concepts. Scaled prototypes are engineered to represent the most important phenomena related to the fluid-structure interaction. Nevertheless, in the case of floating wind turbines, the interaction between turbine aerodynamics and platform hydrodynamics presents important challenges that need to be considered. A new hybrid system focused on floating wind turbine tank testing is presented in this paper. It is based on a variety of fans, a multi-fan, which allows the high-fidelity reproduction of a wide range of wind turbine aerodynamics. One of the main advantages of the new methodology proposed, is the possibility to include other loading aside from thrust and wind turbine torque. The most important aerodynamic loads are represented. In fact, it has been demonstrated that wind turbine thrust can be captured with less than 0.5% error compared to the theoretical value. It is also possible to simultaneously model the thrust, torque and shear moments on the rotor within an error below 2%. The multi-fan system deploys a fast rate of change, up to 35N/s, guaranteeing the scaled dynamics. In unsteady wind speeds using 4% of atmospheric turbulence, 94% of the total energy is captured.

1 Introduction

The worldwide energy demand is continually increasing at the same time as the awareness of the impact of fossil fuels on the climate. Low carbon policies are being implemented in most countries. Europe has a target of 20% energy consumption from renewable sources by 2020 and 27% by 2030. Renewable energy represented more than 85% of the new power installation in 2010 in Europe where 21.1 GW of 24.5 GW installed were from clean energy sources [1].

The main clean energy sources come from solar and wind energy, the latter being the most installed energy technology worldwide, accounting for 51% of the total power capacity installation in 2016 with 12.5 GW. The majority of the installed power capacity comes from onshore wind. However, the offshore market will play an important role in the near future, as evidenced by the increasing installed capacity over the last several years. Offshore wind technologies are still in the development phase, where further technological advances will make commercial projects more economically viable.

There are numerous advantages of offshore wind energy. The wind speed offshore tends to be steadier and stronger than onshore. This implies a more reliable source of energy due to its higher energy yield. Even small variations in wind speed significantly increase the energy production. However, the majority of the offshore wind potential is located at sites with more

34 than 60 meters of water depth [2]. More than 4000GW of wind resource is located at sites where
35 fixed offshore structures become economically infeasible. Because of this, numerous floating
36 offshore wind concepts are under development, thanks to the strong support shown from a
37 regional to European Level.

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39 Floating wind turbine design is one of the most challenging offshore engineering tasks at this
40 time, mainly because it involves a highly-coupled aerodynamic and hydrodynamic system.
41 Wave tank testing of scaled models is often a mandatory approach to understanding the dy-
42 namics of the Wind Turbine–Platform–Mooring system. Laboratory results are often used for
43 Ultimate Limit State analysis, as well as for numerical model calibration and validation. Scale
44 model tests provide accurate information about main processes involved in the system [3].
45 Wave tank test results are usually the basis for hydrodynamic numerical coefficient calibration,
46 i.e., added masses and damping on simplified models [4], verifying critical cases and quantify-
47 ing dynamic uncertainties.

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49 A scaled model provides a solution where fewer resources are used and less risk is taken,
50 without compromising the dynamics of a full-scale Floating Offshore Wind Turbine (FOWT). It
51 provides valuable feedback to the developers to validate the design and numerical tools. It is
52 also a standard practice during the development of new floating wind turbines [5]. It has been
53 used for several projects and for a range of substructures, i.e., Statoil Hywind or Kabashima
54 Island or semisubmersible as WindFloat or Gusto Trifloater.

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56 The quality of the results of the scaled campaigns are directly related to the resemblance of
57 the scaled model to the full-scale design. Thus, the corresponding masses and system inertias
58 must be accurately represented, along with the external loading and corresponding frequencies
59 acting on the system. The Froude-scale method is extensively used, since the hydrodynamic
60 similitude is conserved, capturing the wave loading correctly. On the other hand, the Froude-
61 scale method does not properly represent the wind loading problem. Using the Froude-scale
62 method, the Reynolds number varies and it will be much lower than for a full scaled model.
63 Consequently, the aerodynamic forces do not resemble the corresponding scaled loading.

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65 Different methodologies have been investigated in order to match the wind turbine loading.
66 The first approaches developed were based on static lines or cables which represent a static
67 thrust obtained from a thrust curve for a given turbine. The main advantages of this method
68 are: (1) Simple mechanical system, (2) the test layout is easy and quick to prepare and (3) Static
69 wind loads are relatively easy to achieve. However, it has some important disadvantages: (1)
70 The wind loads are static: lack of control or wind variability, (2) the wind loads do not take into
71 account the platform response, (3) inertial problems and (4) no gyroscopic effects.

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73 A second approach is wind loading based on drag discs introduced by [6] and [7] in order
74 to reproduce static wind loading without the problems presented at the static lines. The main
75 advantages of this method are: (1) It is a relatively simple mechanical system, (2) wind loads
76 are relatively easy to calibrate, (3) any wind turbine can be simulated, (4) steady wind loads can
77 be simulated easily for the first part of the thrust curve (below rated speed) and (5) by means
78 of a spinning disk, the gyroscopic effect can also be simulated. While the main disadvantages
79 are: (1) It needs a low turbulence wind generation system, (2) the drag disk generates vor-
80 tex shedding behind the disk: induced vibrations, (3) the wind turbine control system cannot
81 be simulated and (4) the negative damping cannot be simulated (wind speed above the rated
82 speed).

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84 A third approach, based on scaled wind turbines, has some examples in [8] and [9]. The Eu-
85 ropean project named INNWIND summarizes an extensive review of the different methods. It
86 pays special attention to the different rotor-based turbine modelling projects carried out up to
87 2014. The main modelling strategy observed was Froude-scaled thrust forces based on modi-
88 fied blades. Some experiments tried to represent not only the thrust force, but also the torque.
89 Specific blades modified due to low Reynolds numbers were developed, including, in some
90 specific cases, a pitch control system to better represent the turbine aerodynamics [8]. The main
91 advantages of this method are: (1) The system better represents the real scheme of a wind tur-
92 bine, (2) anomalous phenomena due to vortex shedding are avoided and (3) gyroscopic forces
93 can be easily included. However, the main disadvantages are: (1) It is a relatively complex
94 mechanical system, (2) wind loads are relatively complex to calibrate, (3) each turbine has a
95 specific blade geometry, low flexibility, (4) it needs a low turbulence wind generation system,
96 (5) wind variability (intensity and directional variations) cannot be simulated with standard
97 wind generation systems, (6) limited wind turbine control strategies can be tested.

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99 Alternative technologies have been developed during the last few years. They try to repre-
100 sent the aerodynamic performance of a wind turbine without using wind generators; where
101 the wind turbine loads are obtained by means of real-time synchronized numerical models
102 and the loading is applied by means of an actuator: fans or winches. Those solutions are also
103 known as Real-time Hybrid Test (RTHT) or hardware in the loop (HIL). Over the last few years,
104 different RTHT solutions have been developed in order to include the complexity of the wind
105 turbine control system in the wave basin. One of the first technologies was presented by [5].
106 It is based on a dynamically controlled fan which represents the thrust force of the wind tur-
107 bine. It runs coupled in real time with FAST, which receives information from the mockup, like
108 movements, and provides the reaction of the wind turbine according to the wind time series
109 used and the control system implemented. Similar to this method, [10], [11] and [12], pre-
110 sented an alternative technology based on a real time controlled set of winches, strategically
111 connected to a framework located on top of the tower. The originality of this method is that it
112 is able to reproduce all the aerodynamic load components, not only the thrust forces. However,
113 this method requires a specific auxiliary structure where all the winches are located. Therefore,
114 it increases the complexity of the test setup and not all the basins may be suitable for this kind
115 of setup.

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117 The present paper responds to the demand for advanced methods capable of solving the
118 Froude-Reynolds scaling conflict, and able to easily represent transient conditions and control
119 strategies modelled at laboratory scale, which are not yet feasible with physical wind genera-
120 tors. The present paper presents a novel method based on a set of fans which makes possible
121 the reproduction of the most important aerodynamic loads, and a wide range of wind aerody-
122 namic loading conditions with high fidelity.

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124 This paper has been organized as follows: first, the multi-fan system is described, including
125 hardware and the control dedicated software; second, the calibration methodology is shown;
126 third, a detailed validation of the results is described; and finally, the main conclusions will be
127 summarized.

2 Multi-fan system description and characterization

2.1 Hardware

The multi-fan system has been designed to be used as an actuator for offshore wind platforms. It consists of up to six fans controlled by electro-servo-motors, which are governed by a tailored controller system. Each of the propellers produces its own thrust, which generates a force and a momentum capable of reproducing the varied loading of a wind turbine.

Figure 1: Isometric CAD view of multi-fan including details of propeller rotation and resultant force direction

An isometric view of the multi-fan can be observed in figure 1. In the presented configuration, six motors are mounted where four of them are oriented to produce pure thrust force, along the y axis, while two are rotated to create a moment around the y axis to resemble the wind turbine torque. The blue arrow defines the normal vector to the propeller plane, thus the force direction.

The motors produce an electromagnetic force around its normal plane, as a result of the torque applied to spin the motors, which can be clockwise or anticlockwise, depending on the propeller spinning direction. The electromagnetic torque is compensated by assembling the motors following a clockwise - anticlockwise sequence, thus neutralizing the effect of motor torque around the y axis. In figure 1, the red and green arrows represent the direction of rotation of the motor.

The propellers are mounted on a lightweight brush-less motor, T-motor antigravity, figure 2. Its design provides a good ventilation between poles avoiding overheating. The high performance of the motor is kept in any working region, which makes it suitable for this purpose. The blades, also produced by T-motor, are constructed as a sandwich design of carbon fibre, permitting high loading and low inertia with high efficiency and stability. Three sizes are currently used ranging from 8" to 12".

Figure 2: Multi-fan propeller sizes: left 12", middle 8" and right 10"

155 The multi-fan's propellers are mounted in a polylactic acid (PLA) structure. It is built up by
 156 a 3D printer permitting the parameterisation of the design variables. The structure geometry
 157 permits the embedding of the tri-axial load cell, where a dent of the outer dimensions of the
 158 load cell is included in the design. The tri-axial load cell is connected to the multi-fan structure
 159 and the tower of the mock up by means of bolts. On the right panel in figure 3, the multi-fan-
 160 load cell connection can be observed.

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162 The propellers are assembled in a series of clamps connected to 40 mm diameter carbon fibre
 163 tubes. **The stiff connection introduces high frequency vibration, which is remedied by includ-**
 164 **ing dampers at the joints. A detailed view of the propeller-clamp assembly via the damper can**
 165 **be noticed on the left panel of figure 3.** The multi-fan electronics, ESC (Electronic Servo Con-
 166 troller), micro-controller and power supply are compactly placed into a case, avoiding relative
 167 movements and minimizing problems deriving from electronics malfunctioning.

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Figure 3: Detailed view. Left panel: propeller assembly via damper. Right panel: Tri-axial load cell embedding in multi-fan and RNA weight adjustment system

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170 **Excluding the load cell, the total weight of the multi-fan is 1.9 Kg. A weight moving system is**
 171 **designed to add the often heavier scaled RNA mass. The center of gravity can also be adjusted**
 172 **by moving the added mass horizontally. An example of the system can be observed in the right**
 173 **panel of figure 3.**

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Figure 4: Overview of multi-fan actuator system

175 The system which governs the fan can be split into two blocks: control, or software, and power
 176 electronics. The control part consists of a PC which handles the real-time computation. Then,
 177 the PC transmits the signals to the controller (relay) which transforms it into a discrete sig-
 178 nal. Finally, the discrete signal is sent to the ESC, which actuates directly to the motor. The
 179 ESC receives a digital signal with a specific pulse width, whose longitude controls the power
 180 provided to the motor. The power electronics part includes all the necessary elements, which
 181 provides voltage to different components. The relay's digital output signals are used to control
 182 the electricity flow to the ESC which, at the same time, is transmitted to the motors.

183 2.2 Software

184 The software scheme implemented in the multi-fan is the so-called Hardware In the Loop
 185 (HIL), figure 5. It consists of the coupling of a simulation tool, which provides the loading
 186 on the wind turbine, with the actuator device applying the scaled force on the physical model
 187 [5]. The 6 degree of freedom dynamics of the platform are captured in real time and used as
 188 an input in the aero-servo-elastic software. The values are transformed into full-scale positions
 189 and angles to compute the full scale loads in the software. Finally, the loads are scaled to the
 test model and replicated in the system by means of the multi-fan.

Figure 5: HIL scheme Implementation

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The SIL includes a series of calculations which need to be computed according to the time-scale Froude laws. This can be challenging when complex codes, such as aero-servo-elastic, are used to obtain the turbine loading. In order to optimize the computational time, a parallel software architecture governs the multi-fan. A multi-processor computer running in Linux provides a light interface and powerful performance for multitasking. Thus, the multithreaded architecture permits the parallelization of the different processes, avoiding sequential action and improving the overall response time of the actuator. An overview of the hardware in the loop control scheme is shown in figure 6.

Figure 6: Representation of Parallel multi-fan architecture implementation

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One thread is dedicated to acquiring data from the platform motion acquisition system up to 100 Hz via a wireless connection. The full-scale computation and load scaling is handled by a second thread. The aero-elastic computation is done when a new value of the tracking system is acquired or at the user-defined time step. The signal processing is also calculated in this thread. The software architecture permits the integration of different methods to calculate the wind turbine load from steady loading to complex dynamics, derived from the turbine controller-platform interaction. A third thread is dedicated to shutting down the multi-fan when the test temporization, governed by Froude scale time laws, has not been accomplished, ensuring the detection of anomalous events.

209 2.3 Multi-fan calibration

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The scaled loading provided by the controller must be transformed into individual forcing. A formulation is needed to obtain the force of each propeller, which fulfills the overall loading demanded of the multi-fan. The presented equations assume that 6 motors are mounted with 4 of them placed (T1, T3, T4 and T6) in the perpendicular plane to produce, ideally, pure thrust force in the y direction, figure 7. It is assumed that the nominal forcing of all the propellers is equal for the same control signal (PWM).

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The total loading of the multi-fan is defined as a function of each propeller force and its geometric disposition. A tri-axial load cell, which is located beneath the turbine's frame, is used as a reference system. Then, the distances and angles of each propeller to the reference system describes the equations that govern the actuator. An overview of the reference system, distances and motor numbering convention can be observed in figure 7.

Figure 7: Multi-fan geometric description

223 The motors 1, 3, 4 and 6 cannot contribute to the aerodynamic moment or torque, M_y . The
 224 motor 2 and 5 are turned oppositely at β , both contributing to M_y , see figure 1 and 7. Thus, the
 225 relation that defines the force of the second and fifth motor, T_2 and T_5 , to generate a specific
 226 torque, M_y is defined by:

$$T_2 = \frac{M_y}{2 I_{y1} \sin(\beta)}; \quad T_5 = T_2. \quad (1)$$

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228 Where M_y is the desired aerodynamic moment, I_{y1} is the distance between the tri-axial load
 229 cell and motor 2 and 5, and β the out-of-plane angle of the motor, see figure 7. Based on the
 230 hypothesis that all the propellers have a similar performance, the force generated by propellers
 231 1, 3, 4 and 6 can be related with the total thrust of the multi-fan, F_y , as a function of the
 232 generated force by the out-of-plane motors, T_2 and T_5 , as follows:

$$F = \frac{F_y - 2 T_2 \cos(\beta)}{4}. \quad (2)$$

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235 Where F is the individual forcing of the motors mounted in the perpendicular plane if only
 236 thrust force is reproduced. The general expressions which define the force that must be gener-
 237 ated by propellers 1, 3, 4 and 6 for a given loading can be defined as follows in equation 3 and
 238 4:

$$T_1 = F - \frac{0.5 M_x}{2 I_z} + \frac{0.5 M_z}{2 I_{y2}} \quad T_3 = F + \frac{0.5 M_x}{2 I_z} + \frac{0.5 M_z}{2 I_{y2}} \quad (3)$$

$$T_4 = F + \frac{0.5 M_x}{2 I_z} - \frac{0.5 M_z}{2 I_{y2}} \quad T_6 = F - \frac{0.5 M_x}{2 I_z} - \frac{0.5 M_z}{2 I_{y2}}. \quad (4)$$

239 Once the formulation for any load combination is defined, the relation between the Pulse Width
240 Module (PWM) and the force of the motor is needed. The process is known as calibration and
241 is achieved by operating a motor from minimum to maximum PWM while recording its force.
242 The signal in figure 8 is normalized using its maximum recorded force value, y axis, and its
243 range of PWM in operation, x axis.

Figure 8: Calibration of a standalone motor-propeller: Normalized characteristic curve

244 Determining the relation between the discrete signal and the force for one motor permits the
245 verification of the accuracy of the presented formulation. A linearly increasing thrust over 600
246 seconds is commanded to test the accuracy of the formulation, where, a comparison between
247 the objective and measured thrust is depicted in figure 9. The presented case commands pure
248 thrust to the multi-fan, while the rest of the moments remain null. Thus, motors 2 and 5 are not
249 active.

Figure 9: Comparison demanded and measured thrust using analytical formulation without corrections

The objective and measured thrust are normalized by the maximum objective thrust value, found at 600 seconds. It is possible to observe the mismatch between the objective and measured force. The formulation is valid for low ranges of thrust but as the thrust increases, the difference between the objective and measured signals grows. The maximum difference observed is 14% at the highest objective thrust.

Therefore, the presented formulation presents limitations for large thrust values. Three phenomena lead to the mismatch in forcing: (1) motor-propeller assembly uncertainty, (2) motor-propeller performance variability and (3) nearby rotor interaction also known as aerodynamic couplings. Next, a discussion and analysis of these sources of error is summarized.

2.4 Multi-fan calibration: resolving assembly and manufacturing uncertainties and nearby propeller interaction

The first two sources of error are related to manufacturing and assembly imperfections of the multi-fan structure and the motor-rotor behaviour which are exaggerated at high regimes of operation. The motor and blades used on the multi-fan are designed with high precision, but small differences between propellers induce differences on the measured loading. First, minor measurement errors introduce uncertainty to the algorithms which control the system and second, differences in the forces generated by different motor-rotor assemblies have been experienced for the same PWM. Thus, the system needs to take into account small variations between propellers in the algorithm.

It is possible to quantify that phenomena by measuring the standalone force of each motor at different operating ranges and comparing them. The results presented in this paper only consider one propeller size, 10", operating at three different regimes: regime 1 = 1200 PWM, regime 2 = 1600 PWM and regime 3 = 2000 PWM. It should be noted that the operation of the motors ranges from 1050 to 2000 PWM, therefore the three selected regimes cover a vast range of the system.

Table 1 presents the difference between the standalone force measured by each of the motors and the normalized mean value of the four of them. The last row in table 1 shows the force deviation, difference between the motor producing lower and higher loading. It is possible to observe that the deviation increases as the total loading increases.

Table 1: Standalone deviation per motor compared to the total mean value

	Regime 1	Regime 2	Regime 3
T1	98 %	94 %	93 %
T3	102 %	106 %	107 %
T4	103 %	107 %	109 %
T5	97 %	93 %	93 %
Deviation	6 %	14 %	16 %

The hypothesis, all the propellers produce the same forcing at the same control signal, is proven wrong in table 1. From now on, each of the motors is characterized independently to ensure that the same force is being commanded. Thus, each propeller, n has its own $PWM_n - T_n$ relation.

288 The aerodynamic influence due to the proximity of another rotor is defined as the nearby wake
 289 rotor effect. The effect of an adjacent motor wake modifies the inflow of the motor, varying
 290 the loading compared to its standalone value. It is possible to demonstrate this phenomenon
 291 by comparing the individual and collective performance of the multi-fan. The loading is
 292 measured when the motors are operating simultaneously and compared with its theoretical
 293 value, obtained by the multiplication of individual forcing and number of acting motors. Table
 294 2 presents the results for thrust loading, only motors 1, 3, 4 and 6 operating.

Table 2: Comparison of the theoretical and measured forcing values

	Regime 1	Regime 2	Regime 3
Error [-]	-2.5 %	-6.6 %	-14.5 %

295 The influence of the aerodynamic coupling between the motors alters the generated force and
 296 decreases the total force. The influence is higher when the loading is higher, where a difference
 297 of 14.5 % is found in regime 3. Thus, the measured force is 14.5% lower than the commanded
 298 one. For lower regimes, the interaction of the motors presents a minor effect, 2.5% deviation,
 299 as seen in table 2 for regime 1.

300 Both effects can be addressed by defining empirical factors that correct the uncertainties pre-
 301 viously presented. Thus, a hybrid formulation is used where the theoretical fundamentals are
 302 corrected with empirical variables. The corrections are defined for each motor as a function of
 303 PWM. Thus, if T_n is the generated force for the n th motor, the new formulation is:
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$$T'_n = T_n K_{n1} K_{n2}. \quad (5)$$

305 Where K_{n1} is the correction due to motor-assembly uncertainty and K_{n2} is the nearby wake
 306 rotor effect of the n th motor. The K_{n1} correction is obtained from the measured values from the
 307 tri-axial load cell where the forces and moments for each of the motors provides the character-
 308 istic distances to the reference system, K_{n1} is a static correction which does not change during
 309 operation.
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311 **The motor-assembly uncertainty correction, K_{n1} , is independent of the loading applied by the**
 312 **multi-fan. On the other hand, the nearby wake rotor effect correction, K_{n2} , differs between the**
 313 **two load sets: pure thrust or thrust and aerodynamic moment simultaneously. If only thrust is**
 314 **commanded, a thrust sequence like the one presented in figure 9 but with all the thrust motors**
 315 **operating simultaneously is commanded and C_1 is obtained by:**
 316

$$C_1 = \frac{T_c}{T_m}. \quad (6)$$

317 **C_1 corresponds to the ratio between T_c , the commanded force and T_m , the measured force. If**
 318 **$C_1 = 1$, the nearby wake rotor effect is non-existent, while for larger values of T_c the propellers**
 319 **have an influence on each other, as seen in table 2. C_1 provides the correction for every T_c so :**
 320 **$T_c = T_m$.**
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324 If M_y , in equation 3, equals zero, the empirical correction K_{n2} is equal to C_1 since there is no
 325 influence on the thrust by the aerodynamic moment. The correction factor is the same for the
 326 motors: T_1, T_3, T_4 and T_6 .

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 328 If aerodynamic moment is included in the formulation, $R_1 \neq K_{n2}$ since propellers 2 and 5,
 329 see figure 7, affect the flow of their adjacent motors. In order to obtain the correction, first, the
 330 relation $F - M_y$ is gathered from the steady state curve. Then, F and M_y , are commanded
 331 simultaneously and permit the definition of C_{2n} as:

$$C_{2n} = \frac{T_c(M_y)}{T_{m_n}}, \quad (7)$$

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334 where C_{2n} is the n th nearby wake rotor correction when thrust and torque are commanded,
 335 $T_c(M_y)$ is the thrust as a function of commanded aerodynamic torque and T_{m_n} is the thrust
 336 measured on the n th motor. The sequence is commended asynchronous to motor 2 and 5. Thus,
 337 it is possible to calculate the force of each of the motors in the thrust plane due to the load im-
 338 balance produced around the x axis. The C_{2n} correction is unique for each of the motors since
 339 it depends on the relative position, upstream or downstream, to motor 2 and 5 respectively. In
 340 the presence of aerodynamic torque, $K_{n2} = C_1 + C_{2n}$.

341 2.5 Loading Capacity for assorted loading

342 The technology presents a series of advantages that are beneficial for wind turbine loading
 343 simulation at laboratory scale. It has a good performance in both static and dynamic response,
 344 presenting the following advantages: (1) thrust accuracy and stability, (2) inclusion of assorted
 345 aerodynamic moments simultaneously, (3) fast rate of change and (4) response due to high
 346 frequency unsteady wind speed is captured. Additionally, the lightweight design and the pos-
 347 sibility of adding mass in the RNA allows the performance of experiments at different test
 348 scales preserving the scaled properties.

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350 In order to prove the multi-fan capacity to simulate a range of turbines at different scales,
 351 the maximum thrust, four propellers; and thrust and torque, six propellers; for the available
 352 propeller sizes have been measured. It should be noted that the values presented in 3 are
 353 approximate numbers, since the thrust and torque are dependent on the assembly distances
 354 between propellers and can be modified depending on the test requirements. It must also be
 355 noted that another configuration can be defined, where 6 motors are oriented to produce thrust,
 and the reference values provided in table 3 would be higher.

Table 3: Multi-fan maximum loading capacity approximation

Propeller Size	Thrust \approx	Thrust and Torque[Nm] \approx
8 "	12 N	10 N / 1.5 Nm
10 "	35 N	28 N / 3 Nm
12 "	42 N	37 N / 5 Nm

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357 The NREL 5MW wind turbine [13] is used to illustrate the steady state thrust and torque and
 358 the RNA weight for different scales in table 4. The results provide a reference of the capabilities
 359 of the multi-fan loading presented in table 3.

Table 4: Example RNA Weight, thrust and torque of NREL 5MW at different scales

Scale	RNA weight [kg]	Thrust [N]	Torque [Nm]
1:50	2.8	5.7	0.67
1:40	5.5	13.7	1.8
1:30	12.9	32.6	5.7
1:20	43.7	110.0	29.1

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The scaled weight of the NREL 5MW is not a limiting factor for the multi-fan in the proposed scales. However, the current system might have to be redesigned to carry large weights present on the bigger scales, for example 43.7 kg at 1:20 scale. In the presented scales, the thrust can be reproduced up to 1:20 scale and the torque up to 1:40. However, motors 2 and 5 could be displaced further to the tri-axial load cell to achieve a torque equivalent to a 1:30 scale. As seen in table 3, the maximum thrust is 42N and the maximum torque is 5Nm, using the 12" size propeller.

368 3 Results

369 This section presents results of the multi-fan system. The tested configuration has 6 motors, where motors 2 and 5 are turned towards $\beta = \pm 90^\circ$. At assembly, the distances of the propellers to the load-cell are: $I_{y1} = 400mm$, $I_{y2} = 200mm$ and $I_z = 346mm$. The tests are carried in a fixed foundation test bench and the simulated wind turbine considered stiff.

373 3.1 Steady States

374 In order to present an example of the accuracy of the technology, the steady state curve of the NREL 5MW at 1:40 scale is reproduced. First, only thrust is reproduced, figure 10, and secondly thrust and torque are simultaneously reproduced, figure 11. The tests are run for 60 seconds covering the complete operational range of the wind turbine but plotted against wind speed for a better comprehension.

Figure 10: Multi-fan Operational State Reproduction: Thrust of NREL 5 MW 1:40

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In the lone thrust case, figure 10, the multi-fan presents a maximum relative error of 0.5%. The second case, figure 11, when simultaneous loading is being applied also presents good agreement between the demanded and measured thrust and torque, finding a maximum relative error of 1.5 % at rated wind speed.

Figure 11: Mutli-fan Operational State Reproduction: Simultaneous Thrust and Torque of NREL 5MW 1:40

383 *3.2 Unsteady wind speed validation*

384 The capacity to rapidly change the thrust determines the quality of the results for unsteady
 385 wind speed cases where high frequency fluctuations are not always correctly captured in scaled
 386 models. In order to determine the response of the multi-fan, two tests were carried out. First, a
 387 wind step simulation through the different motor regimes and, then, an unsteady scaled wind
 388 speed simulation.

389 Figure 12 presents the positive and negative rate of change. The positive rate of change value
 390 is achieved by means of (1) the individual acceleration of the motor increases the overall re-
 391 sponse of the multi-fan and (2) the optimized electronics architecture permits a fast response
 392 to the motors. On the other hand, the negative fast rate of change is achieved thanks to the low
 393 inertia of the propellers.

Figure 12: Step Response Simulation: max. and min. rate of change and resultant torque

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395 The maximum rate of change of the multi-fan is obtained when the 6 fans are positioned for
 396 thrust loading obtaining 35 N/s positive rate of change and 15N/s when decelerating. The
 397 published results by [5] of a 6MW turbine determined that the maximum measured slope in
 398 a full-scale turbine simulation is 140 kN/s, 13.8 N/s at the used scale, using 12.7 m/s mean
 399 wind speed and a turbulence intensity of 19%. The multi-fan system copes with the require-
 400 ments stated by other authors thanks to a higher rate of change than the one demanded at real
 401 scale for unsteady wind speed simulations. The system shows 2.5 times the positive force ac-
 402 celeration than the one requested by a 6MW turbine at 1/40 scale. On the right panel of figure
 403 12, the resultant torque during the step sequence shows the good performance of the multi-fan
 404 when only thrust is commanded, when ideally the value would be nul.
 405
 406 FAST [14] is used to create a turbulent series based on the reference turbine, NREL 5MW, for
 407 one hour. The mean wind speed is 10 m/s with a turbulence intensity of 14%. The test is scaled
 408 at 1:40 and reproduced by the multi-fan. On figure 13, it is presented the complete time-series
 409 comparison. The multi-fan performance is better analyzed if a shorter time-series section is
 chosen. Two different zoom-in are shown in figure 14.

Figure 13: One hour scaled thrust series NREL 5MW 1:40

Figure 14: Zoom in time series scaled thrust NREL 5MW 1:40 zoom in two 60 seconds period

411 Figure 14 shows a good agreement between both time series. It demonstrates the multi-fan ca-
 412 pabilities for the reproduction of unsteady forces. It is possible to observe how the high thrust
 413 deployment correctly represents the unsteady aerodynamics, capturing the thrust fluctuation
 414 and its peaks. The time series provides a good comprehension of the multi-fan response, but
 415 further analysis is needed. The power spectral density of both signals shows the frequency and
 amplitude response of the multi-fan compared to its demanded force.

Figure 15: Spectral comparison demanded vs measured thrust

416
 417

418 Figure 15 presents the comparison between the demanded and measured spectrum of the
 419 scaled thrust series. Both series present a similar behaviour up to 1 Hz in response and am-
 420 plitude. The high energy content found in the lower frequencies is correctly represented by
 421 the multi-fan presenting a difference below 4 % of the total system energy. The multi-fan can
 422 also capture the higher frequency content but presents some differences in the amplitude of
 423 the response. The presented result is only shown for a single simulation but similar energy
 424 discrepancies are obtained for different wind speeds and turbulence seeds.

425 3.3 Simultaneous loading

426 Other relevant loads besides the thrust can be modelled by the multi-fan. A sensitivity anal-
 427 ysis by [10] concluded that yaw moments change the standard deviation of the platform yaw
 428 motion up to 80%. The inclusion of this loading on early design phases provides valuable in-
 429 formation on the structure-wind turbine response. The NREL 5 MW model is run using a wind
 430 speed of 10 m/s including a vertical power law shear profile of 0.14. The difference of the wind
 431 speed value along the blade azimuth position provides a cyclic loading on the wind turbine
 432 rotor at 3P frequency.

433

434 The thrust and torque on the rotor are kept constant during the demanded time-series. On
 435 the other hand, azimuthal variation due to shear changes the moments around x and z axis,
 436 based on the previously defined reference system in figure 7.

437

438 The multi-fan presents some deviation of the theoretical thrust and torque fixed value. The
 439 fluctuations are, in both cases, around the mean value and not exceeding 2.5% of relative error.
 440 The M_x and M_z moment are correctly represented by the multi-fan, where a small time-lag is
 441 observed.

442

Figure 16: Complex Loading Demonstration NREL 5MW, mean wind speed 10 m/s shear vertical profile 0.14

443

444 The periodic loading in both directions is captured at 3P frequency. Thus, the combined theo-
 445 retical and empirical formulation for any loading on the multi-fan is demonstrated as valid.

446 4 Conclusions

447 The present paper presents a new approach for scaled aerodynamic loading simulation in the
 448 wave basin. It is based on an array of teleoperated fans that constitutes a multivariable, multi-
 449 fan system. The multivariable system presents some challenges, which are stated in this paper.
 450 The analytical formulation, presented at the beginning of section 2.3, does not produce accurate
 451 results, as shown in figure 9. The influences of the different singularities, like the aerodynamic
 452 coupling between fans, are discussed in section 3 as well. The concluding formulation consists
 453 of a modification of the first formulation which includes two additional empirical factors de-
 454 fined as a function of the motor and its operational regime.

455

456 The accuracy and capabilities of the multi-fan have been demonstrated comparing the objec-
 457 tive loading and measured for a variety of cases. The new technology presents relative errors
 458 of 0.5% when thrust is the only commanded force. The system presents a high rate of change
 459 of the force, up to 35 N/s for positive acceleration and up to 15N/s in the case of negative
 460 accelerations. Both of them provide enough reactivity to reproduce variable wind time series.
 461 In the case of unsteady wind speed time series it has been evidenced that the system is capable
 462 of reproducing up to the 96% of the energy of the wind spectra. The systems evidenced some
 463 limitations above 1-2Hz, where the system is not able to capture the energy of the demanded
 464 time series.

465

466

467 The system here presented, in comparison with other wind aerodynamic loads systems based
468 in fans, it is able to reproduce simultaneous loading. Two cases have been presented in this
469 study. First, the results of simultaneous torque and thrust of the NREL 5 MW at 1:40 scale
470 shows deviations of 1.5% of its theoretical value. Then, the 3P rotor loading due to vertical
471 wind shear profile is shown presenting errors below 2.5% and a short time-lag.

472
473 To conclude, the technology proposed here showed good engineering capabilities for mim-
474 icking wind turbine dynamics at laboratory scale. It may help to understand the importance of
475 turbine control strategies for floating offshore wind turbines. Low cost experimental methods
476 will enable advanced and detailed tests to mature floating offshore wind technologies.

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